

EMF Exposure from MU-MIMO Wi-Fi Systems in Indoor Environments: Comparative Analysis of Precoding Schemes

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Abstract—This study investigates electromagnetic field exposure from a 5 GHz MU-MIMO access point in an indoor environment. Using ray-tracing simulations, we compared Maximum Ratio Transmission (MRT) and Zero Forcing (ZF) precoding. Results show that while increasing the user count reduces E-field levels for served users, ZF is significantly more effective. Crucially, ZF maintains high SINR levels, whereas MRT signal quality declines sharply. Bystander exposure remains relatively stable, indicating that ZF optimizes communication performance without increasing the EMF footprint.

I. INTRODUCTION

Latest-generation wireless local area networks (WLANs), such as IEEE 802.11ac/ax, employ beamforming and multi-user multiple-input multiple-output (MU-MIMO) techniques to improve spectral efficiency and throughput by directing radiated power more efficiently and serving multiple simultaneous users through dedicated spatial streams. Consequently, the spatial distribution of electromagnetic fields transmitted by access points is altered, which influences EMF exposure. In this study, we examine how downlink EMF exposure in an indoor environment is affected by the applied precoding scheme and the number of simultaneous users.

II. METHODS

A. Environment, Transmitter and Propagation Modeling

The modeled environment is an indoor laboratory with an area of approximately 63 m². An access point (AP) is centrally mounted on the ceiling at a height of 2.8 m. A detailed three-dimensional model of the environment was created using Blender.

The access point (AP), operating in the 5 GHz band with a maximum transmit power of 23 dBm, employs dipole antenna elements arranged in uniform rectangular array configurations. Two array geometries were considered: a 2×2 and a 3×2 arrangement. The antenna system was modeled in MATLAB using the array geometry and element radiation patterns.

Electromagnetic propagation was simulated in MATLAB using its built-in ray-tracing tool [1] that employs the shooting and bouncing rays method to identify LOS and NLOS paths between the transmitter and the receiver. For NLOS paths, the rays interactions with the 3D model of the environment were limited to two reflections and one diffraction.

B. MIMO Channel and Beamforming techniques

Beamforming techniques are differentiated by the precoding matrix that adjusts the phase and amplitude of the signals at each antenna element of the transmitter. The precoding matrix is a function of the channel matrix between the transmitter and the intended users.

The channel coefficient $h_{m,k}$ between the m^{th} antenna element and the k^{th} user is calculated from the ray tracing simulations as [2]:

$$h_{m,k} = \sum_{ray=1}^{N_{m,k}} \sqrt{\frac{P_{ray}}{P_m}} e^{i\theta_{ray}} \quad (1)$$

where $N_{m,k}$ is the total number of rays arriving from element m to the position of k and P_m is the power transmitted by the element m while all other elements transmitted zero power. P_{ray} and θ_{ray} are the power and phase shift of each ray at the receiver. The channel matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times M}$ consists of all the channel coefficients, where M is the number of antenna elements and K is the number of simultaneous users.

Depending on the beamforming technique, the precoding matrix is:

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{cases} \mathbf{H}^H & \text{MRT} \\ \mathbf{H}^H (\mathbf{H}\mathbf{H}^H)^{-1} & \text{ZF} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where $(\cdot)^H$ indicates the Hermitian transpose. \mathbf{G} is then normalized and scaled such that its squared Frobenius norm equals the maximum transmit power.

C. E-Field and SINR Calculation

The transmitted signal vector from the antenna array is:

$$\mathbf{x} = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{s} \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbb{C}^{K \times 1}$ contains the transmitted symbols for each user, assumed to have unit average power. The received signal at user k position is:

$$y_k = \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{x} + n_k = \mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{G}\mathbf{s} + n_k \quad (4)$$

where \mathbf{h}_k is the channel vector for user k , corresponding to the k^{th} row of the channel matrix \mathbf{H} and n_k denotes the noise power.

The instantaneous received power at position k is given by:

$$P_{r,k} = |y_k|^2 = |\mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{G}\mathbf{s}|^2 \quad (5)$$

from which we derived the time averaged rms value of the electric field as:

$$E_k = \sqrt{\frac{4\pi Z_0}{\lambda^2}} |\mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{G}| \quad (6)$$

where Z_0 is the impedance of free space and λ the wavelength.

The Signal-to-Noise-plus-Interference-Ratio (SINR) is calculated as [3]:

$$\text{SINR}_k = \frac{|\mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{g}_k|^2}{\sum_{j=1, j \neq k}^K |\mathbf{h}_k \mathbf{g}_j|^2 + n_k} \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{g}_i is the i^{th} column of the precoding matrix, \mathbf{G} .

D. Exposure Assessment

To investigate the influence of beamforming techniques and user density on exposure distributions for both intended users and bystanders, the electromagnetic field exposure assessment was conducted at 146 discrete positions uniformly distributed across the indoor environment, with a grid spacing of 0.5 m, excluding areas obstructed by physical clutter. Each grid position was sequentially assigned as the primary user location, while in multi-user scenarios involving two to three simultaneous users, additional user locations were randomly selected from the remaining positions. The electric field strength was calculated at all positions for both MRT and ZF precoding schemes, for scenarios with one to three simultaneously served users and for both antenna array configurations (2x2 and 3x2).

III. RESULTS

The electric field (E-field) distributions for the Maximum Ratio Transmission (MRT) and Zero Forcing (ZF) precoding schemes were evaluated for varying user densities (one to three users). Fig. 1 presents the distribution of electric field strength for users and bystanders under MRT and ZF precoding as a function of the number of simultaneously served users, for the two antenna configurations. For intended users, the median E-field decreases with increasing user count for both precoding schemes. Under MRT, the median user E-field values decrease by 2.2 dB and 3.4 dB for the 2x2 and 3x2 antenna configurations, respectively, when increasing the number of simultaneously served users from one to three. A more pronounced reduction is observed for ZF, where median values decrease by 8.5 dB and 6.6 dB for the 2x2 and 3x2 configurations, respectively. For bystanders, the median E-field remains relatively stable across all user densities and for both precoding schemes, with a small increase of approximately 1 dB between one and three users for both antenna configurations. The ranges also show limited variation, indicating that changes in user density and precoding scheme primarily affect exposure levels at intended user locations, while bystander exposure shows only minor variation.

In Fig. 2, the two precoding schemes are compared in terms of the signal-to-noise-plus-interference ratio (SINR) as a function of the number of simultaneously served users for both antenna array configurations. For MRT beamforming, the SINR decreases sharply when two or more users are served simultaneously. In contrast, ZF beamforming maintains significantly higher SINR levels across all user densities, with median values remaining above 50 dB even as the number of users increases. Overall, ZF provides a substantial SINR improvement compared to MRT in multi-user scenarios, reflecting its ability to effectively suppress inter-user interference.

Figure 1. Users and Bystanders E-field Distribution for MRT and ZF Beamforming with 2x2 and 3x2 Antenna Arrays.

Figure 2. SINR comparison for MRT and ZF Beamforming with 2x2 and 3x2 Antenna Arrays.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

This study analyzed the impact of MU-MIMO beamforming techniques on indoor EMF exposure using realistic ray-tracing simulations. The results demonstrate that the ZF precoding scheme is significantly more effective than MRT for high-density indoor networks. While both schemes show a reduction in E-field levels at intended user locations as the user count increases, this reduction is more pronounced under ZF. Importantly, ZF achieves lower exposure levels while maintaining high SINR through effective interference suppression, whereas MRT suffers from a sharp decline. Throughout these scenarios, bystander exposure remains relatively stable regardless of the precoding scheme or user density. These findings suggest that ZF offers a dual benefit by optimizing multi-user communication performance while simultaneously reducing the EMF exposure for active users.

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